

Survival of *Ditylenchus angustus* in diseased stubble

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Rice disease Tiem Dot San caused by *Ditylenchus angustus* has occurred not only in deepwater rice in the Mekong Delta but also in double-transplanted rice of the main crop and in transplanted rice following the main crop.

Diseased rice hills with the panicle

still enclosed in the leaf sheath were collected (20-30 tillers/ hill) from an infested field and left on the surface of a grassy, nonflooded soil in late October 1976. Each week, three diseased plants were taken out randomly and the average percentage of surviving nematodes per plant was estimated by extracting the nematodes from each plant into 50 ml water in a petri dish and counting with a 1-ml counting slide.

The percentage of active nematodes decreased rapidly after harvest. After 3

weeks, the population was 40%. From 4 to 10 weeks the percentage was lower and stabilized as the nematodes adapted to dormant conditions. In early February 1977, no live nematodes were found.

The result shows the ability of *Ditylenchus angustus* to survive from the main rice crop to the crop transplanted in November and December and the need to find control measures against nematodes in crop residue. ■

Survival of sclerotia of rice stem rot fungus

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Sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae*, rice stem rot fungus, grown on sterilized rice culm pieces for 10 months were placed in soil layers 5, 15, and 25 cm deep in 5-cm-diameter polyethylene columns. The columns were buried in sandy clay loam (pH 7.3) with the top of the column at field level. Three water treatments were used: continuously dry; continuously wet to field capacity; and 3 days continuously wet, 10 days dry. Columns were removed at 4, 8, and 12 weeks and sclerotia retrieved by washing over an 80-mesh screen. Sclerotia viabil-

ity was tested by growing them on water agar containing penicillin and streptomycin sulfate at 3,000 ppm each (see figure).

Viability of sclerotia declined more in the surface soil. After 12 weeks, losses were 100% in dry soil, 91% in wet, and 84% in alternately wet and dry. At 15 and 25 cm depths, sclerotia viability was not much affected in wet and alternately wet and dry soil. In dry soil, viability was reduced to 30% at 15 cm depth and 0% at 25 cm. Pronounced loss in germinability of sclerotia in dry soil would suggest effects of desiccation, solar radiation, starvation, or other factors. ■

Viability of sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae* on paddy stubbles under dry or wet soil conditions.

Weed hosts of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Saw., a sheath rot pathogen of rice

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The host range of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Saw., the rice sheath rot pathogen, has not been widely studied. Because the disease often occurs in severe forms in almost all rice-growing areas of Kerala, irrespective of the cropping season, investigations on the source of inoculum are important. An initial survey at the Model Agronomic Research Station Farm, Karamana, Trivandrum district of Kerala, in fallow fields during the third crop season showed that two field weeds — *Cyperus difformis* L. and

Echinochloa crus-galli (L.) Beauv. were infected naturally with the rice sheath rot pathogen. The symptoms were identical to those on rice and pathogenicity tests of isolates from the weeds showed that they were highly pathogenic to rice.

Artificial inoculation tests at the College of Agriculture, Vellayani, screened out more weed hosts of the pathogen. Uninfected wetland field weeds were collected from different localities in the Trivandrum district and raised in earthen pots under controlled conditions. They were artificially inoculated with actively growing mycelial bits taken from a 10-day-old pure culture of the pathogen grown in potato dextrose agar. Mycelial bits of uniform size (5 mm) cut from the dish culture with a cork borer were introduced in the leaf

axils of test weeds. Inoculated plants were kept in above 92% humidity. Symptom development was recorded 5 to 8 days after inoculation.

Of the 10 weed plants tested, 5 — *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Monochoria vaginalis* (BURM. f.) Presl., *E. crus-galli*, *Cyperus iria* L., and *Cyperus teneriffae* Poir — were recorded for the first time as pathogen hosts. ■

Control of helminthosporium leaf spot by foliar sprays

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The effect of chemicals on the control of helminthosporium leaf spot was studied

in a field trial October-February 1980. The randomized block design with 11 treatments and 3 replications used 3- × 1.5-m plots and 20- × 10-cm spacing. Test variety was IR20. Fertilizer was applied at 120-8.75-147.5 kg NPK/ha. P₂O₅ and K₂O were applied as basal dressings; N as urea was applied 1/2 as basal and 1/2 as topdressing. Chemicals were sprayed three times: 30, 45, and 60 days after transplanting.

The data indicate that spraying 0.1% carbendazim significantly controlled helminthosporium leaf spot disease (see table). ■

Effect of chemicals on the control of helminthosporium leaf spot disease. Ambasamudram, India.

Treatment	Helminthosporium infection	
	%	Transformed value
Carbendazim 0.1%	6.5	14.7
Copper oxychloride 0.25%	8.8	17.3
Edifenphos 0.15%	8.8	17.3
Zineb 0.25%	9.5	18.0
Agrimycin 0.025%	9.0	17.4
Urea 1.0%	7.7	16.1
DAP 1.0%	11.1	19.4
Kc1 1.0%	9.4	17.8
Carbofuran at 0.5 kg a.i./ha ^a	8.8	17.1
Carbendazim SST ^b 0.04%	8.3	16.7
Control	12.0	20.3
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.05 level)		2.19

^aCarbofuran was applied 10, 25, and 40 days after transplanting. ^bSprouted seed treatment = sprouted seeds were soaked in carbendazim solution for 15 minutes before sowing.

Rice blast disease outbreak in Sinjai and Bulukumba, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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The Indonesian Government released Semeru (IR2307-247-2-2-3, CRI 3/IR1561-228-3-3) in 1980 for planting in both low and high elevations. As part of a rainfed wetland pilot production program (Lappo Ase) in South Sulawesi, Semeru was planted at elevations of 300-1,000 m in Sinjai District and at 700-1,000 m in Bulukumba district.

In Bulukumba, rainfall varied from 151 to 521 mm June-July (8-18 rainy days), with July overcast most days and nights. In the more than 900 ha planted to Semeru and fertilized with 100 kg N/ha (urea) and 37.5 kg P₂O₅ triple superphosphate, neck blast infection ranged from 6 to 85%. About 80 ha had more than 85% neck blast infection.

At Sinjai, rainfall ranged from 60 to 658 mm June-September (7-20 rainy days). Of about 390 ha planted to Semeru and fertilized with 87.5 kg N/ha (urea and ammonium) and 37.5 kg P₂O₅/ha, 3.5 ha suffered early from serious leaf blast. Eventually the entire area was seriously affected. Observations during heading to hard dough stage showed that neck blast infection varied from 1 to 100% on about 390 ha. More than 100 ha were hopperburned during the filling stages. ■

Association of rice tungro spherical virus and rice tungro bacilliform virus with the disease in Janakpur, Nepal

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Rice plants showing symptoms of yellow leaf discoloration, plant stunting, and delayed flowering were found at Hardinath Agricultural Farm, Janakpur, Nepal. The disease occurred in circular field patches several meters in diameter.

Electron microscopic observations of dip preparations revealed polyhedral

Electron micrograph showing rice tungro spherical virus and rice tungro bacilliform virus (arrows) in dip preparation from leaf sap infected with rice tungro disease from Janakpur, Nepal.

particles about 30 nm in diameter and bacilliform particles about 30-35 nm in diameter, both 100-300 nm in length (see figure). This shows that rice tungro disease in the Janakpur area is caused from double infection by both rice tungro spherical virus and rice tungro bacilliform virus, as has been reported in the Philippines, Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia. ■

Rice stem nematode disease in Vietnam

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Rice stem nematode disease has become a serious concern in Vietnam. Department of Plant Protection surveys 1975-1980 showed that the disease was focused in the Mekong Delta, the largest (more than 2 million ha) rice production area.

Each year *D. angustus* causes important losses in thousands of hectares of

deepwater rice and double-transplanted rice (yield losses of 50-100%). Some damage is done in improved rice areas.

The disease appears to be serious in the deepwater area between two branches of the Mekong (Hau-Giang and Tien-Giang Rivers) and in provinces along the rivers (An-Giang, Hau-Giang, Long-An, Bon-Tre). It has not been reported in coastal and upland areas.

The nematode has caused great damage to rice crops in Cuu-Long, Dongthap, An-Giang Provinces. At the end of 1974, hundreds of hectares of deepwater rice in the Due-Thanh district were totally lost. Infested areas increased to